

Distance	Bedload			Total no of charcoal-BL
	Sample name	>125 μm	<125 μm	
0	YRU	4	8	13
5	YRP	0	11	11
26	YSM2	0	0	0
36	YRCA	0	161	161
48	YRS21-15	3	3	6
94	YYB	4	19	23
130	YRS21-12	0	25	25
158	YKB	4	7	11
189	YRS21-13	32	0	32
243	YRS21-11	13	598	611
262	YPC	4	77	81
288	YRS21-09	14	27	41
292	YRS21-08	0	0	0
308	YAJ	0	60	60
314	YRS21-06	0	6	6
337	YTD	152	199	214
342	YRS21-07	0	0	0
364	YMB	27	308	335
381	YHMB	4	0	4
432	YSNB	8	14	22
463	YBV	6	0	6
503	YMK	0	4	4
518	YJP	168	0	168
597	YPG	15	348	363

Sample name	Floodplain fine		Total no of charcoal-FF
	>125 μm	<125 μm	
YRU	3	10	13
YRP	0	2	2
YSM2	0	0	0
YRCA	9	10	19
YRS21-15	0	0	0
YYB	10	4	15
YRS21-12	0	9	9
YKB	1	8	9
YRS21-13	12	9	21
YRS21-11	11	5	16
YPC	30	7	37
YRS21-09	0	0	0
YRS21-08	0	2	2
YAJ	28	184	212
YRS21-06	3	2	5
YTD	17	232	249
YRS21-07	0	0	0
YMB	9	23	32
YHMB	8	190	198
YSNB	29	101	130
YBV	43	152	195
YMK	4	88	92
YJP	4	79	84
YPG	17	189	206

Total no of charcoal-BL+FF
26
13
0
180
6
37
34
19
53
628
118
41
2
272
12
463
0
367
202
152
201
96
252
569

642	YWB	20	17	37
701	YMHB	4	21	25
821	YEB	11	15	25
825	YRS21-02	17	164	181
863	CRS21-01	0	29	29
909	YCC	0	0	0
941	YAR	12	131	143
1000	YKP	0	13	13
1065	BRS21-01	3	0	3
1069	YHB	5	53	57
1079	YBC	0	0	0
1101	YRS21-05	0	0	0

YWB	21	165	186	223
YMHB	18	368	386	411
YEB	0	16	16	42
YRS21-02	0	0	0	181
CRS21-01	0	0	0	29
YCC	0	14	14	14
YAR	15	49	64	207
YKP	6	0	6	19
BRS21-01	0	0	0	3
YHB	5	31	36	94
YBC	0	8	8	8
YRS21-05	3	1	4	4

Table 2: Microscopic charcoal count (>125 μm and <125 μm) in the bedload and the floodplain (per volume of sediments) deposits from different location across the Yamuna mainstream.